

MODERN ASPECTS OF THE INFLUENCE OF FETOPLACENTAL INSUFFICIENCY AND OZONE THERAPY ON THE CONDITION OF NEWBORNS

Urinova Iroda Sunnatillayevna

Master's student Department of Pediatrics

Bukhara State Medical Institute

Mukhammedova Shakhnoza Tolibovna

DSc, Associate Professor

Department of Pediatrics Bukhara State Medical Institute

Abstract

Fetoplacental insufficiency is one of the most important complications of pregnancy associated with impaired placental circulation, chronic fetal hypoxia, and adverse perinatal outcomes. In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to the use of ozone therapy as an additional therapeutic method for improving placental blood circulation and reducing fetal hypoxic damage. This literature review analyzes modern data concerning the influence of fetoplacental insufficiency on the condition of newborns and evaluates the potential therapeutic effects of ozone therapy in obstetric and neonatal practice.

Keywords: fetoplacental insufficiency, ozone therapy, newborn, chronic fetal hypoxia, placenta, neonatal adaptation, pregnancy complications.

Introduction

Fetoplacental insufficiency (FPI) remains one of the leading causes of perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide. The condition develops as a result of impaired functional interaction between the maternal organism, placenta, and fetus, leading to disturbances in oxygen and nutrient transport. As a consequence, chronic fetal hypoxia, intrauterine growth restriction, metabolic disorders, and neonatal adaptation impairment may occur.

According to modern obstetric and neonatal research, fetoplacental insufficiency complicates a significant percentage of pregnancies and is especially common among women with preeclampsia, anemia, chronic cardiovascular diseases, endocrine disorders, and infectious-inflammatory conditions. Placental dysfunction significantly increases the risk of premature birth, fetal distress syndrome, low birth weight, and neonatal neurological complications.

The placenta is a unique temporary organ responsible for gas exchange, metabolic transport, hormonal regulation, and immunological protection of the fetus. Structural and functional placental abnormalities lead to insufficient fetal oxygenation and accumulation of metabolic products, contributing to fetal distress and developmental disorders.

One of the main pathogenetic mechanisms of fetoplacental insufficiency is chronic hypoxia. Long-term oxygen deficiency negatively affects the central nervous system, cardiovascular

system, respiratory adaptation, and immune response of the newborn. Numerous studies demonstrate that children born from pregnancies complicated by FPI often exhibit respiratory distress syndrome, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, impaired thermoregulation, and delayed postnatal adaptation.

In recent years, considerable scientific interest has been directed toward improving therapeutic approaches for fetoplacental insufficiency. Alongside conventional pharmacological treatment, ozone therapy has gained attention as a promising additional therapeutic method.

Medical ozone is a mixture of ozone and oxygen possessing antioxidant, antihypoxic, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and microcirculatory effects. Ozone therapy is believed to improve tissue oxygenation, activate antioxidant defense systems, enhance rheological properties of blood, and normalize placental circulation.

Several studies indicate that ozone therapy may improve uteroplacental blood flow, reduce manifestations of fetal hypoxia, and enhance fetal adaptive mechanisms. The procedure also demonstrates positive effects on maternal metabolism and endothelial function, which are often impaired in complicated pregnancies.

The influence of ozone therapy on neonatal outcomes has become an important area of modern perinatology research. According to published data, newborns whose mothers received ozone therapy during pregnancy often demonstrate better Apgar scores, improved respiratory adaptation, lower incidence of hypoxic complications, and reduced need for intensive care support.

However, despite encouraging clinical results, questions regarding the mechanisms of ozone therapy, optimal treatment protocols, safety profiles, and long-term neonatal outcomes remain insufficiently studied. Therefore, comprehensive evaluation of the influence of fetoplacental insufficiency and ozone therapy on newborn condition remains highly relevant.

Conclusion

Fetoplacental insufficiency remains one of the major causes of adverse perinatal outcomes and neonatal adaptation disorders. Chronic fetal hypoxia associated with placental dysfunction negatively affects respiratory, neurological, and metabolic status of newborns.

Modern data indicate that ozone therapy may improve placental circulation, reduce oxidative stress, and enhance neonatal adaptation. Rational use of ozone therapy in complex management of fetoplacental insufficiency may contribute to improved perinatal outcomes and reduction of neonatal complications.